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AI Business Models: A Solution towards a Sustainable Innovation

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Abstract:

Artificial intelligence (AI) has emerged as a transformative force in modern business, driving innovation and addressing critical sustainability challenges. This paper explores the integration of AI into business models as a solution for fostering sustainable innovation. The study highlights key characteristics of AI business models while addressing challenges such as skills shortages, data management issues, and ethical concerns. Despite barriers to implementation, the findings underscore AI's potential to redefine value creation and drive sustainable growth.

Key words: Artificial Intelligence (AI), Business Models, Solution, Sustainable innovation.

Résumé:

L'intelligence artificielle (IA) s'est imposée comme une force de transformation dans les entreprises modernes, en stimulant l'innovation et en relevant des défis cruciaux en matière de durabilité. Cette recherche explore l'intégration de l'IA dans les modèles d'affaires en tant que solution pour favoriser l'innovation durable. L'étude met en évidence les principales caractéristiques des modèles d'entreprise de l'IA tout en abordant des défis tels que la pénurie de compétences, les problèmes de gestion des données et les préoccupations éthiques. Malgré les obstacles à la mise en œuvre, les résultats soulignent le potentiel de l'IA à redéfinir la création de valeur et à stimuler la croissance durable.

Mots clés: Intelligence Artificielle (IA), Modèles d'affaires, Solution, Innovation durable.

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INTRODUCTION:

The rapid evolution of artificial intelligence (AI) from a niche technological advancement into a transformative element reshaping industries, economies and societies worldwide has forced many businesses, big corporations such as Google.LLC, Apple. Inc, Microsoft.etc., to invest in the research and development R&D in AI, increasing significantly the AI market size . As businesses seek to enhance efficiency, increase productivity, drive innovation while addressing global challenges, AI has become a disruptive force that not only reshaped traditional business models, but also created whole new business landscapes, new models, offering new opportunities to foster sustainable innovation. These AI-based business models are becoming powerful tools for improving efficiency, reducing environmental impact and promoting long-term sustainability in business practices.

Their diversity from traditional business models implementing AI solutions to enhance productivity and boost performance to business models built and based on AI itself (Bouadila, Boucha, 2024), businesses are shifting towards this new paradigm in order to achieve sustainability and more profitability, thus, creating value through more sustainable practices, and more sustainable innovation in efficient and effective way.

This modest research paper is a sequel to a previous research (Bouadila, Boucha, 2024). We aim to shed light on AI business models, exploring their transformative potential in fostering sustainable innovation and how AI can redefine value creation, delivery and capture, focusing on its application in green tech and resource optimization.

The study seeks to answer the following question: *What are the characteristics of AI business models that promote sustainable innovation in industries? and what challenges do these industries face as barriers to implementing AI business models?*

To achieve this, the research will use a literature exploration and analysis approach, drawing on existing literature, databases and resources to examine how AI business models are being adopted and the barriers encountered when implementing them.

By analyzing relevant data, and showcasing practical examples, this study will provide a better understanding of the potential of AI-based business models to promote sustainability, while addressing the challenges that industries face when integrating them.

1. Artificial Intelligence Business Models:

There is no consensus on the exact definition of this new concept precisely, opinions vary but what is approved is the fact that it is a merger of two concepts which are Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Business Models (BM).

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is defined as the ability of a digital computer or computer-controlled robot to perform tasks that are typically associated with human activities. (Khalfallah and Bendjelloul, 2023).

This technology goes beyond human-like robots, chatbots such as ChatGPT, Gemini..etc. Studies show that the AI market size is increasing significantly as it is expected to reach USD 1,811,747.3 million by 2030 with a compound annual growth rate CAGR of 37.3% globally and 45.7% in Middle East and Africa, since all the attention shifts to these technologies' capacities at unlocking great potential not only for businesses but also for humanity.

Figure01: Global artificial intelligence market, 2017-2030 (US\$M)

Source: elaborated by the authors based on data from [Grand View Research](#)

Figure 02: Middle East & Africa artificial intelligence market, 2017-2030 (US\$M)

Source: [\(Grand View Research\)](#)

On the other hand, Business Models (BM) are defined as a schematic representation that refers to the framework or structure that outlines how a company creates, delivers, and captures value. It provides a strategic roadmap for how a company operates and generates profits. (Ferdin, 2018).

In addition, a business model can be seen as the system of organizational, managerial, and operational logics through which an organization transforms resources into results, turning inputs into outputs through a series of activities and projects (Federico & al, 2024).

Merging these two concepts together by implementing AI tools or solutions in how a company operates and generates profits, in its process of creating, delivering and capturing value, will create a whole new paradigm, a new concept that transforms basic and traditional business models, which is the AI business model.

AI based business models can be defined as business models that use AI technology to drive innovation, improve customer experiences and automate processes.

This implementation will generate two categories or let's say two patterns of leveraging AI tools in business models, all depends on to what extent AI technologies are implemented:

First, the AI solutions are implemented in some specific areas or operations of the business models to enhance performance, 72% of companies globally have adopted AI in at least one business function.(McKinsey Global Survey, 2024)

Figure 03: Organization that have adopted AI in at least one Business Function,

Source: elaborated by the authors based on data from [McKinsey Survey, 2024](#)

Second, the whole business model and the company’s activity is based on AI solutions (Bouadila, Boucha,2024), and that’s the emphasis of our study such as the Subscription-Based Model, AI-as-a-Service (AIaaS), Freemium Model, AI-Powered Consulting Model, Platform-as-a-Product Model...etc. In terms of segment, software accounted for a revenue of USD 70,453.6 million in 2023. and Services business model is the most lucrative solution segment registering the fastest growth during the forecast period.

(Grand View Research)

2. Characteristics of AI business models:

When it comes to AI business models the characteristics vary, since AI is an umbrella term for different tools most of which are machine learning (ML) techniques, from supervised ML, to unsupervised ML, reinforcement learning and even, deep learning (Jorzik & al, 2024)

The implementation of those tools or solutions in a business model is not only disruptive, but also creates a new and unique business model with specific characteristics that depend on the extent and the part in which AI is implemented. Some of which are:

- **Integration of AI Technologies:** Obviously the first characteristic is integrating AI tools and technologies. AI business models leverage advanced technologies such as

machine learning, data analytics, and automation to improve operational efficiency and scalability. This integration allows businesses to automate processes, analyze vast amounts of data, and enhance decision-making capabilities.

- **Automation centric:** Using AI solutions automate repetitive tasks, reduce manual intervention, and improve efficiency. Though this characteristic may show concern to some, as they consider the threat of AI replacing humans, but actually, studies show that AI complements rather than it replaces most jobs as innovation and technological advancements contribute significantly in the creation of new jobs. A recent study by economist David Autor found that 60% of today's workers are employed in occupations that didn't exist in 1940. This implies that more than 85% of employment growth over the last 80 years is explained by the technology-driven creation of new positions, (Goldman Sachs Research, 2023).
- **Data-Driven or Datafication and Personalization:** Data is the cornerstone of AI business models, used to generate insights, optimize processes and deliver personalized experiences, providing tailored recommendations and enhancing customer satisfaction.
- **Ecosystem Oriented:** AI Business models focus on creating value through interconnected networks. These networks can be platforms fostering ecosystems of users, developers, and partners, or simply a network of businesses and technologies, algorithms based on data. The increased usage improves the usage for all stakeholders. An example is Amazon Web Services (AWS) offers AI tools that integrate with other services to build an ecosystem.
- **Innovation Focused:** Artificial Intelligence has been linked to innovation since the break of dawn, and since business models are all about creating value, implementing AI enables creating new value propositions and developing unique and innovative product or services that were not possible before, but this characteristic at the same time often seem disruptive with traditional business models and processes.
- **Predictive and Proactive Capabilities:** Processing a large amount of data in a short time, with analytical capabilities that goes beyond normal, AI business models are characterized by their ability to analyze data to predict trends, future, thus optimizing the decision making process, and also being proactive face of different external or internal changes making it easier for businesses to adapt, mitigate risks and seize opportunities.

- **Scalability:** Once AI models are trained, they can be deployed at scale with minimal incremental cost. AI business models adapt and handle an increasing workload or market demand, large amounts of data without compromising performance and functionality.

3. Challenges and Barriers in the Implementation of AI driven Business Models:

As any technology, adopting AI solutions may be difficult for certain businesses as they may face some challenges that can be considered as barriers and sometimes the reason for failure of the whole implementation process. Some of these challenges are:

- **Insufficient Skills and Expertise:** A survey revealed that 68% of IT leaders consider a lack of skilled professionals as a significant barrier to AI implementation (DigitalizationWorld, 2024). Dealing with new advanced technologies demands trained and skilled human resources, and the shortage of competent experts will interrupt the process of implementing those solutions and getting a reverse impact and cause employees resistance.
- **Data Management:** Data management represented the largest challenge to AI development in 2023. Companies around the world find difficulties to handle and manage the large amount of data required and generated by AI use. (B. Thormundsson, 2024).
- **Safety and Security:** one of the top challenges exposed and discussed in the literature about artificial intelligence in general and AI business models in particular is the safety provided by these tools and the security of data stored with these solutions. Ensuring the protection of data from security-breaches or any other possible threat is crucial.
- **Ethical and Regulatory concerns:** Another crucial aspect of using AI is ensuring that those systems operate without bias and comply with ethics and morality.
- **Lack of Infrastructure:** lack of infrastructure to process data in real time presents a big challenge for 65% of organisations (DigitalizationWorld, 2024).

The presented figure showcases the broader concept of AI business models in the literature, highlighting the characteristics, challenges, applications, implications and the triggers of AI business models.

Fig 04: Integrated view of AI-driven Business Model Innovation-BMI, (Jorzik & al, 2024)

Source: (Jorzik & al, 2024)

4. Sustainable Innovation:

Innovation is an umbrella term with many definitions that has undergone many changes over years, known as the process of creating, establishing or simply introducing new ideas, new products, new services, new processes...etc, in order to provide or offer something new and creative with significant value and impact. From traditional innovation to sustainable innovation, authors and researchers focused on this evolution highlighting four fields of innovation that will help to support sustainable development goals, including traditional innovation, eco-innovation, social innovation, and the ideal sustainable innovation (Hoang & al, 2021).

Starting with traditional innovation, a term that refers to innovations with minor implications for society and the environment. These innovations focus on profit maximization and improving performances.

Then we have eco-innovation, an innovation that aims to find solutions to environmental concerns and issues but with less emphasis on social problems, which is the opposite of social

innovations that focuses mainly on social concerns with less importance on environmental challenges.

And finally, the ideal sustainable innovation, a balance between both eco-innovation and social innovation, a reconciliation between innovative economic development and sustainable development, a form that deals with both environmental and social challenges equally.

Sustainable innovation can be defined as a type of innovation that seeks to provide a suitable approach to make benefits to society and the environment while delivering positive economic outcomes (an innovation based on the triple bottom line and highlights the three foundations of sustainable development). (Hoang & al, 2021).

5. AI business models and Sustainable innovation:

Crossing the two concepts together, studies show that AI in general can be considered as a solution to a sustainable innovation and place businesses in the dimension of sustainability.

Sustainable AI is a solution that helps minimizing waste, pollution, optimizing resources and a tool to counter global warming (Capgemini Research Institute report, 2022).

Same goes for AI business models. On one hand, these models aim to enhance efficiency, optimize resources, reduce waste, pollution and counter global warming...etc, as previously mentioned in the characteristics of these models. Through AI tools and solutions, companies are able to improve their commitment to sustainability. The results of using AI tools and solutions may be represented as the following:

- **Energy Efficiency:** AI-enabled systems can improve energy efficiency by up to **30%**, particularly in smart grids and buildings. (Rozite, Miller, Oh, 2023).
- **Carbon Emission Reduction:** AI-powered solutions have the potential to reduce global greenhouse gas emissions.
- **Route optimization and fleet management:**AI for route and fleet management can help reduce fuel consumption and carbon emissions (Capgemini Research Institute, 2020)
- **Sustainable Investments:** Companies using AI for sustainability saw a **67%** improvement in environmental performance metrics. In the future, AI is expected to reduce GHG emissions by 16% and improve power efficiency by 15% in the next three to five years.(Capgemini Research Institute, 2020).

On the other hand, with artificial intelligence, it has become easier to address environmental and societal challenges, and actually these technologies have laid the foundation for creating

businesses based on AI with a sustainable impact as their activity aims to solve ecological or societal problems.

As an example, the British “*CarbonChain*” company, an innovative platform based on sustainability with an AI driven business model, according to the company’s website, focuses on offering accurate carbon emission data for companies to track and lower their carbon footprint in supply chains.

Another example of an AI driven business model based on sustainable innovation is the Irish mobile app “*Evocco*” that offers personalized insights using AI solutions that analyzes products data on the carbon footprint of grocery shopping. Thus, encouraging consumers to make greener choices while shopping.

6. Main Findings:

This study main findings can be summarized in the following points:

- The main characteristics of AI-BM that differentiate them from traditional business models are: **Data driven, Scalability, Automation-centric, Predictive and proactive capabilities, Ecosystem-oriented and Innovation-focused.**
- The AI market is projected to grow from \$196.6 billion in 2023 to \$1.81 trillion by 2030, with a CAGR of 37.3% globally and 45.7% in the Middle East and Africa.
- Sustainable innovation is a form that deals with both environmental and social challenges equally.
- AI business models are solutions towards a more sustainable innovation in their both categories as integrating AI tools will help companies be more committed to sustainability on one hand, and on the other one those models offer the opportunity to create sustainable innovative businesses that deal with the environmental and societal problems while being economically performant.
- Companies using AI for sustainability noticed a 67% improvement in environmental performance metrics.
- Services and software AI based business models dominate the market, offering scalability and accessibility.
- Ethical and technical challenges in AI adoption remain barriers to scalability.
- A survey revealed that 68% of IT leaders consider a lack of skilled professionals as a significant barrier to AI implementation.
- Data management was identified as the largest challenge to AI development in 2023.
- A lack of infrastructure for real-time data processing is a significant challenge for 65% of organizations.

CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, Artificial Intelligence is redefining business models and offering golden opportunities for sustainable innovation. By integrating AI-driven strategies and tools, businesses can enhance efficiency, optimize resource utilization, and minimize environmental impacts. From intelligent automation to predictive analytics, AI enables companies to align economic growth with sustainability objectives, fostering long-term resilience in an increasingly competitive landscape.

However, the successful implementation of AI in business models requires overcoming significant challenges, including data security, ethical considerations, lack of skilled professionals, data management...etc. Additionally, the environmental impact of AI technologies, particularly in terms of energy consumption, demands continuous advancements in green AI solutions to ensure that sustainability efforts remain meaningful and effective.

Despite these challenges, AI remains a powerful driver of transformative change, offering scalable and innovative solutions to address pressing global sustainability concerns. Policymakers, business leaders, and researchers must collaborate to develop frameworks that promote responsible AI adoption while maximizing its potential for sustainable development and more precisely on how these advanced technologies can be the foundation of sustainable innovation that seek to overcome the global environmental and societal challenges while seeking at the same time economic growth and performance as leveraging AI strategically, businesses can not only enhance their competitiveness but also contribute to a more sustainable and technologically advanced future.

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